

Are International Reserves ‘Boon’ to Economy-An Analysis of Composition of Broad Money in Indian Economy in the Post Liberalization Period

Dr Jiji Vijayan

Assistant Professor, Department of Economics, All Saints’ College, Trivandrum

ABSTRACT

The Post Liberalisation Period in the Indian Economy is characterised by a rise in Capital Flows and the prudential management of the Trilemma Policy Variables of Financial Liberalisation, Exchange rates and Money Supply. The rise in International Reserves is a testimony to the active intervention by the Monetary Authority to manage the Exchange Rate in the event of Capital inflows, which has implications on the domestic money supply. The Composition of Broad Money in the Indian Economy in the post-liberalisation period is changing in favour of Net Foreign Exchange Assets, which have implications for money supply and exchange rate management.

Key words: Trilemma, Money Supply, International Reserves, Reserve Money

1.1 Introduction

In the post-liberalisation era, the Indian Economy experiences a significant rise in Capital Flows. The exchange market pressures are associated with increased net capital account flows in the post-liberalisation period. Capital Inflows exert significant exchange market pressures in the economy that are resisted by changes in the exchange rates and an increase in foreign exchange reserves. The significant resistance offered by the Indian Economy to exchange market pressures is testified by the huge accumulation of International Reserves in the post-liberalisation period.

The monetary implication of capital inflows, resistance to exchange market pressures and a rise in International Reserves is evidenced by the changing composition of Reserve Money. To prevent capital inflows from affecting the monetary base, active sterilised intervention through open market operations is pursued in the Indian Economy. Despite the fact that there are high sterilisation efforts to neutralise the impact of Capital Inflows on Reserve Money, the rise in

international reserves is transmitted to Broad Money Supply. The sterilisation efforts by raising reserve requirements of the banking sector had generally been ineffective in preventing capital flows from affecting Broad Money Supply.

1.2 Methodology and Data Source

The present paper examines the Growth of International Reserves, Reserve money and change in the composition of Reserve Money in India.

Secondary Time Series data taken from the various issues of Handbook of Statistics on Indian Economy, published annually by the Reserve Bank of India, Data Database on Indian Economy by RBI are the sources of data. Monthly data from June 1993 to June 2018 on Foreign Exchange Reserves, Reserve Money, Net Foreign Exchange Assets and Net Domestic Assets are used for the trend and composition analysis of the present study.

1.3 International Reserves in India

An increase in International Reserves is experienced when the monetary authority accumulates International Reserves in an effort to arrest the appreciating tendency of the domestic currency in the event of Capital Inflows. This is done by purchasing foreign exchange for the domestic currency. A fall in International Reserves occurs when the monetary authority runs down International Reserves to arrest the depreciating tendency of the domestic currency in the event of Capital Outflow, by selling foreign exchange for the domestic currency.

From Table 1.1, it can be seen that International Reserves fluctuated during the period of study. This is the result of the RBI buying and selling of foreign exchange to stabilise the Exchange Rate. The ratio of IR to GDP_{FC} also fluctuated over the years of the study period. As the International Reserves and the Foreign Currency Assets of RBI rise or fall, it has implications on the composition of Reserve Money and Money Supply, which necessitates Sterilised Intervention on the part of the Monetary Authority.

Table 1.1 Quarterly International Reserves in rupees billion and International Reserves to GDP values for India from 1990 Q2 to 2017 Q2

YEAR	QUARTER	GDP _{FC}	International reserves	IR/GDP
1990	Q2	13478.89	55.28	0.004101
1990	Q3	13527.24	54.52	0.00403
1990	Q4	13575.73	36.79	0.00271
1991	Q1	13623.93	47.76	0.003506
1991	Q2	13671.71	27.4	0.002004
1991	Q3	13855.35	38.76	0.002797
1991	Q4	14038.19	76.48	0.005448
1992	Q1	14221.75	119.79	0.008423
1992	Q2	14405.03	151.71	0.010532
1992	Q3	14610.03	161.59	0.01106
1992	Q4	14814.41	136.98	0.009246
1993	Q1	15018.98	159.74	0.010636
1993	Q2	15223.43	212.4	0.013952
1993	Q3	15466.84	229.22	0.01482
1993	Q4	15709.92	274.85	0.017495
1994	Q1	15953.47	408.38	0.025598
1994	Q2	16196.94	492.32	0.030396
1994	Q3	16492.52	565.84	0.034309
1994	Q4	16787.42	614.87	0.036627
1995	Q1	17081.9	634.97	0.037172
1995	Q2	17377.4	631.41	0.036335
1995	Q3	17723.59	626.07	0.035324
1995	Q4	18070.25	613.22	0.033935
1996	Q1	18416.5	581.29	0.031564
1996	Q2	18763.19	603.28	0.032152
1996	Q3	18965.31	648.73	0.034206
1996	Q4	19166.43	698	0.036418
1997	Q1	19368.56	741.33	0.038275
1997	Q2	19570.31	861.84	0.044038
1997	Q3	19897.37	940.97	0.047291
1997	Q4	20224.25	946.47	0.046799
1998	Q1	20551.43	974.82	0.047433
1998	Q2	20878.27	1042.11	0.049914
1998	Q3	21296.53	1066.46	0.050077
1998	Q4	21713.41	1139.28	0.052469
1999	Q1	22131.81	1200.86	0.054259
1999	Q2	22549.42	1301.63	0.057723
1999	Q3	22783.41	1330.81	0.058411
1999	Q4	23017.56	1359.78	0.059076
2000	Q1	23251.1	1451.34	0.06242
2000	Q2	23484.81	1523.61	0.064876
2000	Q3	23800.78	1500.74	0.063054
2000	Q4	24117.63	1648.03	0.068333
2001	Q1	24433.67	1812.88	0.074196
2001	Q2	24749.62	1888.92	0.076321
2001	Q3	24989.9	1981.77	0.079303
2001	Q4	25229.14	2107.81	0.083547
2002	Q1	25469.17	2361.1	0.092704
2002	Q2	25709.35	2637.58	0.102592
2002	Q3	26221.63	2856.43	0.108934
2002	Q4	26733.03	3116.06	0.116562
2003	Q1	27245.89	3382.8	0.124158
2003	Q2	27757.49	3647.3	0.131399
2003	Q3	28246.8	3888.8	0.137672
2003	Q4	28736.3	4291.67	0.149347
2004	Q1	29225.39	4704.89	0.160986
2004	Q2	29714.64	5212.59	0.175422

2004	Q3	30418.59	5305.73	0.174424
2004	Q4	31122.28	5456.35	0.17532
2005	Q1	31827.03	5732.81	0.180124
2005	Q2	32530.73	5899.88	0.181363
2005	Q3	33308.56	6050.82	0.18166
2005	Q4	34086.78	6179.43	0.181285
2006	Q1	34865.1	6171.98	0.177025
2006	Q2	35643.64	7149.14	0.200573
2006	Q3	36474.32	7365.41	0.201934
2006	Q4	37304.93	7446.88	0.199622
2007	Q1	38135.24	8123.98	0.213031
2007	Q2	38966.36	8253.53	0.211812
2007	Q3	39621.1	9183.58	0.231785
2007	Q4	40276.8	10380.55	0.25773
2008	Q1	40931.42	11603.51	0.283487
2008	Q2	41586.76	12781.84	0.307354
2008	Q3	42480.34	12728.43	0.299631
2008	Q4	43374.07	11994.99	0.276547
2009	Q1	44266.76	12084.55	0.272994
2009	Q2	45160.71	12116.79	0.268304
2009	Q3	46166.46	12901.71	0.279461
2009	Q4	47173.48	12591.42	0.266917
2010	Q1	48179.06	12005.16	0.249178
2010	Q2	49185.33	11776.02	0.239421
2010	Q3	50008.07	12309.99	0.24616
2010	Q4	50830.27	12355.19	0.243068
2011	Q1	51652.78	12650.64	0.244917
2011	Q2	52475.3	12934.23	0.246482
2011	Q3	53186.26	13441.39	0.252723
2011	Q4	53897.11	14374.9	0.26671
2012	Q1	54608.33	13332.17	0.244142
2012	Q2	55319.02	14548.52	0.262993
2012	Q3	56156.12	14485.69	0.257954
2012	Q4	56993.4	14566.23	0.255577
2013	Q1	57830.23	14342.07	0.248003
2013	Q2	58667.93	15061.67	0.256727
2013	Q3	59716.84	16209.2	0.271434
2013	Q4	60766.83	16602.13	0.27321
2014	Q1	61815.91	16962.6	0.274405
2014	Q2	62865.49	17511.1	0.278549
2014	Q3	64145.38	18080.93	0.281874
2014	Q4	65426.68	18558.03	0.283646
2015	Q1	66706.92	19636.3	0.294367
2015	Q2	67986.93	21175.93	0.311471
2015	Q3	69190.92	21720.43	0.31392
2015	Q4	70395.46	21970.23	0.312097
2016	Q1	71599.86	22418.5	0.313108
2016	Q2	72804.57	22855.07	0.313924
2016	Q3	73983.36	23087.7	0.312066
2016	Q4	75162.31	23171.5	0.308286
2017	Q1	76341.32	22986.6	0.301103
2017	Q2	77520.23	23196.37	0.29923
Slope			218.44	0.0034
Intercept			-4824.8	-0.0368

Source: Author's Calculation

Received: 12 October 2025

Revised: 25 October 2025

Accepted: 30 October 2025

Copyright ♥ authors 2025

DOI: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.17502344>

Figure 1.1 Trend Line of International Reserves/GDP_{FC} from 1990 Q2 to 2017 Q2

Figure 1.1 represents the trend line of the ratio of international reserves to GDP. The International Reserves to GDP ratio has a positive linear trend with a slope coefficient of 0.0034 for the period 1990 Q2 to 2017 Q2

1.4 Reserve Money in India

Reserve money is an important variable determining the Money Supply in the economy. The money supply is determined by Reserve Money and Money Multiplier. Money Supply is Money Multiplier times High Powered Money. The sources of the Reserve Money are Net Domestic Assets, and Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the Reserve Bank of India. Net Domestic Assets of the Reserve Bank of India are the sum of Net RBI Credit to Government, RBI's Claims on Commercial and Cooperative Banks, RBI's credit to Commercial sector and Government's currency liabilities to the public. Finally, the Net Non-Monetary liabilities of the RBI are subtracted to arrive at the Net Domestic Assets (NDA) of the RBI.

The NDA of RBI = Net RBI credit to Government RBI's claims on Commercial and Cooperative Banks RBI credit to Commercial Sector Government's Currency Liabilities to the Public – Net Non-Monetary Liabilities of RBI. The components of Reserve Money / Monetary Base are the sum of Currency in Circulation, Other Deposits with the RBI and Bankers' Deposits with the

RBI. The Narrow Money includes the currency with the public, other deposits with the RBI, and demand deposits. The Broad Money (M3) is the sum of Time Deposits and Narrow Money.

Table 1.2 presents the Quarterly and Yearwise mean values of Reserve Money in rupees billion in the Indian Economy from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q3. The year-wise mean value of Reserve Money steadily increased over the years of the study period. The mean value of reserve money for the entire period of study is rupees 8088.61 billion. The CAGR is 12.86, but the AGR fluctuated for the study period. There is a significant rise in the monetary base in the post-liberalisation period in the Indian Economy.

Table 1.2 Quarterly and Yearwise mean values of Reserve Money in rupees billion from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q3

Reserve Money M0						
Year	Quarters				Total	AGR
	1	2	3	4		
1991	.	905.00	895.00	952.00	917.00	15.05
1992	1011.00	1079.00	1060.00	1071.00	1055.00	12.80
1993	1099.00	1185.00	1222.00	1255.00	1190.00	22.52
1994	1346.00	1445.00	1492.00	1549.00	1458.00	18.72
1995	1640.00	1762.00	1764.00	1759.00	1731.00	8.78
1996	1845.00	1933.00	1854.00	1902.00	1883.00	7.22
1997	1893.00	2060.00	2037.00	2085.00	2019.00	12.13
1998	2177.00	2244.00	2241.00	2393.00	2264.00	13.83
1999	2507.00	2602.00	2550.00	2646.00	2577.00	7.14
2000	2694.00	2778.00	2714.00	2859.00	2761.00	11.05
2001	2956.00	3110.00	3054.00	3145.00	3066.00	7.08
2002	2971.00	3372.00	3380.00	3407.00	3283.00	14.56
2003	3562.00	3850.00	3734.00	3896.00	3761.00	14.46
2004	4148.00	4304.00	4259.00	4510.00	4305.00	15.38
2005	4722.00	4959.00	4998.00	5191.00	4967.00	18.02
2006	5490.00	5901.00	5928.00	6130.00	5862.00	25.76
2007	6733.00	7256.00	7598.00	7901.00	7372.00	22.46
2008	8723.00	9106.00	9521.00	8763.00	9028.00	5.60
2009	9167.00	9557.00	9442.00	9969.00	9534.00	21.44
2010	10892.00	11525.00	11737.00	12158.00	11578.00	22.15
2011	13012.00	14541.00	14482.00	14539.00	14143.00	9.76
2012	14992.00	15541.00	15525.00	16033.00	15523.00	2.60
2013	16607.00	15541.00	15525.00	16033.00	15927.00	7.27
2014	16607.00	17123.00	17102.00	17509.00	17085.00	11.55
2015	18417.00	18995.00	19049.00	19770.00	19058.00	7.41

2016	20833.00	21603.00	21746.00	17699.00	20470.00	-4.13
2017	16577.00	19705.00	20632.00	21584.00	19625.00	22.49
2018	23140.00	24696.00	24766.00		24039.00	15.05
Mean					8088.61	
CAGR					12.86	
Slope					206.57	
Intercept					-3451.3	
t value					28.196	
sig					0.000	

Source: Authors' Calculation

Figure 1.2 Trend Line of Reserve Money from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2

Figure 1.2 represents the trend growth of reserve money in the post-liberalisation period from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2. The reserve money experienced a positive trend growth with a slope of 206.57. The reserve money grew at a uniform rate of 206.57% over the quarters for the study period. The significance of the t-value implies that reserve money experienced a significant positive trend growth in the post-liberalisation period. There is a significant trend in the growth of reserve money in the post-liberalisation period.

1.5 Net Domestic Assets of the RBI

Table 1.3 presents the quarterly and year-wise Net Domestic Assets of RBI in rupees billion. NDA is a source of Reserve Money. From 2003, the Net Domestic Assets of the RBI experienced negative values, implying a falling NDA of the RBI. The year 2003 is significant in terms of Net Capital Account Flows into the Indian Economy. It was from 2003 onwards that the effect of liberalisation measures in terms of accelerated capital flows into the economy was perceptible. The monetary authority might have tried to neutralise the impact of increased capital inflows on the monetary base by running down NDA. The falling NDA in the face of capital inflows implies sterilised intervention by the monetary authority through open market operations. The mean value of NDA is rupees -785.826 billion, and the CAGR is -205.554. The AGR of NDA fluctuated for the study period.

Table 1.3 Quarterly and Yearwise mean values of Net Domestic Assets of RBI in rupees billion from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q3

Net Domestic Assets of RBI						
Year	Quarter				Total	AGR
	1	2	3	4		
1991		838.53	822.70	836.55	815.12	
1992	847.13	891.77	863.94	902.85	876.42	7.52
1993	923.34	946.83	964.23	956.69	947.77	8.14
1994	916.24	880.15	851.58	855.71	875.92	-7.58
1995	931.12	1033.07	1043.26	1010.82	1004.57	14.69
1996	1101.68	1180.12	1052.94	1054.90	1097.41	9.24
1997	1007.18	1066.10	966.36	1008.32	1011.99	-7.78
1998	1070.63	1083.22	1052.75	1136.27	1085.72	7.29
1999	1181.08	1182.91	1110.60	1169.48	1161.02	6.94
2000	1116.36	1127.07	1086.74	1119.21	1112.35	-4.19
2001	1016.21	1091.91	947.60	898.96	988.67	-11.12
2002	759.88	613.73	412.35	171.77	489.43	-50.50
2003	0.84	103.95	-236.30	-501.07	-158.15	-132.31
2004	-667.42	-1027.20	-1168.53	-1085.55	-987.18	524.20
2005	-1110.21	-1086.36	-1104.55	-1250.81	-1137.98	15.28
2006	-883.46	-1449.59	-1679.28	-1562.42	-1393.69	22.47
2007	-1548.29	-1184.04	-1775.86	-2725.98	-1808.54	29.77
2008	-3123.54	-4043.13	-3656.04	-3592.65	-3603.84	99.27
2009	-3350.09	-2951.59	-3682.70	-3026.28	-3252.66	-9.74
2010	-1653.30	-861.52	-1214.29	-846.31	-1143.86	-64.83

2011	-305.54	37.32	-778.96	-1530.31	-644.37	-43.67
2012	-252.77	-917.07	-1196.59	-1187.11	-888.39	37.87
2013	-588.86	-516.77	-1393.80	-1547.36	-1011.70	13.88
2014	-1309.15	-1325.17	-1960.91	-2055.46	-1662.67	64.34
2015	-2131.16	-3047.46	-3869.42	-3372.73	-3105.19	86.76
2016	-2848.67	-2579.22	-2728.73	-6928.96	-3771.40	21.45
2017	-7716.66	-4645.13	-4848.83	-4357.84	-5392.11	42.97
2018	-3855.92	-3226.97	-3406.85		-3507.80	-34.95
Mean					-785.826	
CAGR					-205.554	
Slope					-49.58	
Intercept					1976.9	
t value					-14.865	
sig					0.000	

Source: Authors' Calculation

Figure 1.3 Trend Line of Net Domestic Assets of the RBI from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2

Figure 1.3 presents the trend line of the Net Domestic Assets of the RBI. The net domestic assets as a source of reserve money experienced a negative trend growth of -49.58 for the period 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2. The significance of the t-value (0.000) implies that the negative trend growth is highly significant for the post-liberalisation period.

1.6 Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI

Table 1.4 presents the quarterly and yearwise mean values of Net Foreign Exchange Assets of RBI in rupees billion from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q3. The year-wise mean values of NFA steadily increased over the years of the study period, even though the AGR fluctuated. The mean NFA for the study period is rupees 8,803.675 billion. The CAGR is 23.975. The rising NFA is an indication of the rising intervention of the monetary authority in the foreign exchange market and the accumulation of a buffer stock of International Reserves.

Table 1.4 Quarterly and Yearwise mean values of Net Foreign Exchange Assets of RBI in rupees billion from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q3

Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI						
Year	Quarter				Total	AGR
	1	2	3	4		
1991		66.59	72.36	115.76	83.40	
1992	163.99	187.71	195.80	168.07	178.89	114.50
1993	176.11	237.89	257.96	298.16	242.53	35.57
1994	429.28	564.78	640.88	693.68	582.16	140.04
1995	708.71	728.80	720.80	748.33	726.66	24.82
1996	743.05	752.40	800.57	847.22	785.81	8.14
1997	885.61	993.95	1070.68	1077.12	1006.84	28.13
1998	1106.57	1160.42	1188.01	1256.83	1177.96	17.00
1999	1326.41	1418.89	1439.83	1476.98	1415.53	20.17
2000	1577.20	1650.73	1627.67	1740.15	1648.94	16.49
2001	1939.53	2018.59	2106.82	2246.06	2077.75	26.01
2002	2492.25	2758.76	2967.90	3235.68	2863.65	37.82
2003	3561.36	3746.39	3970.40	4397.69	3918.96	36.85
2004	4815.81	5331.51	5427.48	5595.54	5292.58	35.05
2005	5832.45	6045.35	6102.86	6441.94	6105.65	15.36
2006	6373.91	7350.67	7607.17	7696.55	7257.08	18.86
2007	8281.19	8440.57	9373.99	10627.61	9180.84	26.51
2008	11847.06	13149.38	13176.72	12355.98	12632.28	37.59
2009	12517.00	12508.70	13124.61	12995.66	12786.49	1.22
2010	12545.79	12386.88	12951.00	13004.02	12721.92	-0.50
2011	13317.82	13516.99	14384.92	15481.65	14175.34	11.42
2012	14410.72	15465.60	15678.64	15725.94	15320.23	8.08
2013	15580.37	16057.77	16919.15	17580.68	16534.49	7.93
2014	17916.37	18448.07	19062.79	19564.52	18747.94	13.39
2015	20548.26	22042.30	22918.02	23142.24	22162.71	18.21

2016	23681.41	24181.82	24474.62	24627.61	24241.37	9.38
2017	24293.37	24350.45	25481.08	25942.08	25016.74	3.20
2018	26996.11	27922.67	28094.50		27618.17	10.40
Mean					8803.675	
CAGR					23.975	
Slope					253.83	
Intercept					-5374.4	
t value					31.487	
sig					0.000	

Source: Authors' Calculation

Figure 1.4 Trend Line of Net Domestic Assets of the RBI from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2

Figure 1.4 represents the trend growth of Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI. The Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI experienced a positive linear trend with a slope of 253.83. The significance of t values (0.000) implies that the slope of the Net Foreign Exchange Assets is highly significant in the post-liberalization period.

1.7 The ratio of the Net Domestic Assets of the Reserve Bank of India to Reserve Money

To understand the changing source of reserve money, the ratio of NDA to RM is computed as Reserve Money is the sum of NDA of the RBI and NFA of the RBI. From table 1.5, it can be

seen that from 2003 the ratio of NDA to RM is negative. The mean ratio is 0.134, and the CAGR is -193.455. The AGR of NDA to RM fluctuated.

Table 1.5 Quarterly and Yearwise ratio of Net Domestic Assets of the RBI to Reserve Money from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q3

	Quarter				Total	AGR
	1	2	3	4		
1991		0.927	0.919	0.879	0.908	
1992	0.838	0.826	0.815	0.843	0.831	-8.48
1993	0.840	0.799	0.789	0.762	0.796	-4.21
1994	0.681	0.609	0.571	0.552	0.601	-24.50
1995	0.568	0.586	0.591	0.575	0.580	-3.49
1996	0.597	0.611	0.568	0.555	0.583	0.52
1997	0.532	0.518	0.474	0.484	0.501	-14.07
1998	0.492	0.483	0.470	0.475	0.480	-4.19
1999	0.471	0.455	0.436	0.442	0.451	-6.04
2000	0.414	0.406	0.400	0.391	0.403	-10.64
2001	0.344	0.351	0.310	0.286	0.322	-20.10
2002	0.256	0.182	0.122	0.050	0.149	-53.73
2003	0.000	0.027	-0.063	-0.129	-0.042	-128.19
2004	-0.161	-0.239	-0.274	-0.241	-0.229	445.24
2005	-0.235	-0.219	-0.221	-0.241	-0.229	0.00
2006	-0.161	-0.246	-0.283	-0.255	-0.238	3.93
2007	-0.230	-0.163	-0.234	-0.345	-0.245	2.94
2008	-0.358	-0.444	-0.384	-0.410	-0.399	62.86
2009	-0.365	-0.309	-0.390	-0.304	-0.341	-14.54
2010	-0.152	-0.075	-0.103	-0.070	-0.099	-70.97
2011	-0.023	0.003	-0.054	-0.105	-0.046	-53.54
2012	-0.017	-0.059	-0.077	-0.074	-0.057	23.91
2013	-0.035	-0.033	-0.090	-0.097	-0.064	12.28
2014	-0.079	-0.077	-0.115	-0.117	-0.097	51.56
2015	-0.116	-0.160	-0.203	-0.171	-0.163	68.04
2016	-0.137	-0.119	-0.125	-0.391	-0.184	12.88
2017	-0.466	-0.236	-0.235	-0.202	-0.275	49.46
2018	-0.167	-0.131	-0.138		-0.146	-46.91
Mean					0.134	
CAGR					-193.455	
Slope					-0.0106	
Intercept					0.7202	
t value					-17.569	
sig					0.000	

Source: Authors' Calculation

Figure 1.5 Trend Line of the ratio of the Net Domestic Assets of the RBI to Reserve Money from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2

Figure 1.5 represents the ratio of Net Domestic Assets of the RBI to Reserve Money. The ratio of the Net Domestic Assets of the RBI to Reserve Money experienced a negative linear trend with a slope -0.0106 for the period 1991Q2 to 2018 Q2. The negative trend of Reserve Money to Net Domestic Assets of the RBI is significant as the level of significance of t statistic is less than 0.05.

1.8 The ratio of the Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI to RM

From table 1.6, it can be seen that from 2003 onwards, the ratio of NDA to RM is greater than one. The mean ratio is 0.866, and the CAGR is 9.790. The AGR of NDA to RM also fluctuated over the study period.

Table 1.6 Quarterly and Yearwise ratio of the Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI to Reserve Money from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q3

	Quarter				Total	AGR
	1	2	3	4		
1991		0.073	0.081	0.121	0.092	
1992	0.162	0.174	0.185	0.157	0.169	83.90
1993	0.160	0.201	0.211	0.238	0.204	20.25
1994	0.319	0.391	0.429	0.448	0.399	96.13
1995	0.432	0.414	0.409	0.425	0.420	5.12
1996	0.403	0.389	0.432	0.445	0.417	-0.59
1997	0.468	0.482	0.526	0.516	0.499	19.55
1998	0.508	0.517	0.530	0.525	0.520	4.35
1999	0.529	0.545	0.564	0.558	0.549	5.58
2000	0.586	0.594	0.600	0.609	0.597	8.67
2001	0.656	0.649	0.690	0.714	0.678	13.47
2002	0.744	0.818	0.878	0.950	0.851	25.59
2003	1.000	0.973	1.063	1.129	1.042	22.46
2004	1.161	1.239	1.274	1.241	1.229	17.97
2005	1.235	1.219	1.221	1.241	1.229	-0.02
2006	1.161	1.246	1.283	1.255	1.238	0.70
2007	1.230	1.163	1.234	1.345	1.245	0.61
2008	1.358	1.444	1.384	1.410	1.399	12.35
2009	1.365	1.309	1.390	1.304	1.341	-4.15
2010	1.152	1.075	1.103	1.070	1.099	-18.07
2011	1.023	0.997	1.054	1.105	1.046	-4.84
2012	1.017	1.059	1.077	1.074	1.057	1.12
2013	1.035	1.033	1.090	1.097	1.064	0.59
2014	1.079	1.077	1.115	1.117	1.097	3.18
2015	1.116	1.160	1.203	1.171	1.163	5.98
2016	1.137	1.119	1.125	1.391	1.184	1.83
2017	1.466	1.236	1.235	1.202	1.275	7.64
2018	1.167	1.131	1.138		1.146	-10.11
Mean					0.866	
CAGR					9.790	
Slope					0.0106	
Intercept					0.2798	
t value					17.569	
sig					0.000	

Source: Authors' Calculation

Figure 1.6 Trend Line of the ratio of the Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI to Reserve Money from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2

Figure 1.6 represents the ratio of Reserve Money to Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI. The trend of Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI to Reserve Money experienced a positive linear trend with a slope of 0.0106. The positive trend growth of Reserve Money to Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI is significant, with the level of significance of the t statistic less than 0.05.

1.9 Changing Composition of Reserve Money

The changing source of reserve money is a pointer towards sterilization activities in the Indian economy, but it does not measure the extent of sterilization in the economy. The changing source of reserve money in terms of Net Domestic Assets of the RBI and Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI are analyzed by the estimated percentage contribution of these sources to the Reserve Money Stock. The estimated percentage contribution of these sources to the total Reserve Money is calculated from the trend line of the actual percentage contribution. It is hypothesized that there is a compositional change in the source of Reserve Money/ Monetary Base in favour of Net Foreign Exchange Assets from Net Domestic Assets in the post-liberalization period.

From the table 1.7, it can be seen that in 1991, 90.72 percent of the source of Reserve Money came from the Net Domestic Assets of the RBI, and 9.28 percent of the source of Reserve

Money came from Net Foreign Exchange Assets of RBI. As the actual percentage contribution of Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI as a source of Reserve Money rose over the years, there is a corresponding drop in the actual percentage contribution of the Net Domestic Assets as a source of Reserve Money. The rise in the actual contribution of Net Foreign Exchange Assets and fall in Net Domestic Assets is evident since 2003, the period from which the Indian Economy experienced accelerated capital flows. This implies that the rise in Foreign Exchange Reserves; as a result, capital flows were prevented from affecting the Monetary Base by a compensatory fall in Net Domestic Assets of the RBI. Over the years of the study period, the actual percentage contribution of NDA as a source of Reserve Money fell, as the actual contribution of NFA rose over the years from 1991. The actual contribution of NDA as a source of Reserve Money became negative from 2003. The actual contribution of NFA increased steadily over the years until 2010. It was 104.21 in 2003. But in 2010, it fell to 109.88 from 134.12 in 2009. In 2018 the actual percentage contribution of NFA as a source of Reserve Money was 114.55. The estimated percentage contribution of NDA as a source of reserve money in 1991 was 70.31, it fell steadily and became negative from 2008. But the estimated percentage contribution of NFA, which was only 29.69 in 1991, rose steadily over the years and was estimated to be 143.61 in 2018. To test whether the change in the source of Reserve Money in favour of NFA from NDA, the ratio of the estimated percentage contribution of NDA and NFA as sources of Reserve Money was calculated. The calculated ratio was tested by KS Test. But the level of significance of the KS test is greater than 0.05, and the null hypothesis that there is a significant compositional change in Monetary Base in favour of Net Foreign Exchange Assets from Net Domestic Assets is rejected.

Table 1.7 Actual and Estimated Percentage Contribution of the sources of Reserve Money from 1991 to 2018

Year	Reserve Money	Net Domestic Assets of the RBI		Net Foreign Exchange Assets of the RBI		4/6
		Actual	Estimated	Actual	Estimated	
1	2	3	4	5	6	7
1991	100	90.72	70.31	9.28	29.69	2.37
1992	100	83.05	66.09	16.95	33.91	1.95
1993	100	79.62	61.87	20.38	38.13	1.62
1994	100	60.07	57.65	39.93	42.35	1.36

1995	100	58.03	53.43	41.97	46.57	1.15
1996	100	58.27	49.21	41.73	50.79	0.97
1997	100	50.13	44.99	49.87	55.01	0.82
1998	100	47.96	40.78	52.04	59.23	0.69
1999	100	45.06	36.56	54.94	63.44	0.58
2000	100	40.28	32.34	59.72	67.66	0.48
2001	100	32.24	28.12	67.76	71.88	0.39
2002	100	14.60	23.90	85.40	76.10	0.31
2003	100	-4.21	19.68	104.21	80.32	0.25
2004	100	-22.93	15.46	122.93	84.54	0.18
2005	100	-22.91	11.24	122.91	88.76	0.13
2006	100	-23.77	7.02	123.77	92.98	0.08
2007	100	-24.53	2.80	124.53	97.20	0.03
2008	100	-39.92	-1.42	139.92	101.42	-0.01
2009	100	-34.12	-5.63	134.12	105.63	-0.05
2010	100	-9.88	-9.85	109.88	109.85	-0.09
2011	100	-4.76	-14.07	104.76	114.07	-0.12
2012	100	-6.16	-18.29	106.16	118.29	-0.15
2013	100	-6.52	-22.51	106.52	122.51	-0.18
2014	100	-9.73	-26.73	109.73	126.73	-0.21
2015	100	-16.29	-30.95	116.29	130.95	-0.24
2016	100	-18.42	-35.17	118.42	135.17	-0.26
2017	100	-27.48	-39.39	127.48	139.39	-0.28
2018	100	-14.55	-43.61	114.55	143.61	-0.30
Kolmogorov Smirnov Test	Test Statistic	0.162				
	Sig	0.057				

Source: Authors' Calculation

Figure 1.7 Estimated Percentage Contribution of the sources of Reserve Money from 1991 to 2018

From figure 1.7, it can be seen that the estimated percentage contribution of Net Domestic Assets as a source of Reserve Money fell during the study period, and the estimated percentage contribution of Net Foreign Exchange Assets rose during the study period.

1.10 Broad Money in India

Table 1.8 presents the quarterly and yearwise mean values of Broad Money Stock from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2. The Compound Annual Growth rate of Broad Money is 15.44, with the mean value of rupees 43225.75 billion. The AGR fluctuated with the highest value recorded of 28.60 in 2011 and the lowest AGR recorded in 2013 with a value of 3.35.

Table 1.8 Quarterly and Yearwise stock of Broad Money in rupees billion from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2

YEAR	Quarters				Total	AGR
	1	2	3	4		
1991		2760.89	2816.92	2990.69	2856.17	
1992	3127.62	3300.60	3381.62	3497.76	3326.90	16.48
1993	3589.54	3807.84	3882.28	4031.79	3827.86	15.06
1994	4240.02	4508.96	4658.15	4883.94	4572.77	19.46

1995	5076.79	5290.44	5410.53	5595.45	5343.30	16.85
1996	5821.70	6133.47	6287.67	6478.14	6180.25	15.66
1997	6805.97	7163.03	7331.29	7615.70	7229.00	16.97
1998	7971.09	8457.73	8826.29	9193.10	8612.05	19.13
1999	9574.64	10030.67	10351.86	10759.64	10179.20	18.20
2000	11098.83	11643.37	11889.68	12496.30	11782.05	15.75
2001	12934.15	13681.48	13980.03	14368.40	13741.02	16.63
2002	14770.37	15856.23	16284.07	16714.70	15906.34	15.76
2003	17063.15	17858.44	18192.22	18786.85	17975.17	13.01
2004	19625.70	20591.83	20784.53	21258.68	20565.19	14.41
2005	22223.33	23359.69	24045.40	24917.83	23636.56	14.93
2006	26034.07	27694.46	28845.86	29746.63	28080.26	18.80
2007	31720.50	33365.04	35088.95	36670.24	34211.18	21.83
2008	39013.55	40801.35	42195.57	43969.23	41494.93	21.29
2009	46780.41	49373.33	50782.99	52196.19	49783.23	19.97
2010	54762.77	56876.10	58653.67	61320.77	57903.33	16.31
2011	63756.05	76277.29	78003.67	79811.07	74462.02	28.60
2012	82265.65	86237.18	87759.88	91367.96	86907.67	16.71
2013	93923.54	86237.18	87759.88	91367.96	89822.14	3.35
2014	93923.54	97426.42	98784.75	101655.88	97947.65	9.05
2015	104203.18	107870.42	109591.74	112422.96	108522.08	10.80
2016	115329.41	119000.63	121907.13	121673.59	119477.69	10.10
2017	123870.04	127046.86	129583.64	131571.02	128017.89	7.15
2018	136016.04	139898.09	.	.	137957.07	7.76
Mean					43225.75	
CAGR					15.44	
Slope					1236.2	
Intercept					-25839	
t value					25.648	
sig					0.000	

Source: Authors' Calculation

Figure 1.8 Trend Line of Broad Money from 1991 Q2 to 2018 Q2

The trend line of the Broad Money (M3) is depicted in figure 1.8. The Broad Money experienced a significant positive trend growth with a slope coefficient of 1236.2.

1.11 Implications of changing composition of Reserve Money

The influx of Capital Inflows necessitates intervention in the Foreign Exchange Market resulting in accretion of reserves. Foreign exchange market intervention by the accumulation of reserves may lead to sacrifice or trade-off of monetary autonomy for exchange rate stability leading to excessively loose monetary conditions, overheating, and financial system fragilities. To insulate the monetary system from the impact of foreign exchange market intervention and accumulation of reserves, Policy Makers often have to resort to Sterilized Intervention whereby the monetary impact of the intervention is neutralized through a variety of measures like open market operations, increasing bank reserve requirements or transferring government deposits from the banking system to the central bank.

Sterilization is the monetary operation through which a rise in Net Foreign Assets of Central Bank is offset by a decrease in Net Domestic Assets to keep the monetary base constant. The money supply is Money Multiplier times High Powered Money/Monetary Base. The effectiveness of sterilization in curbing excessive inflow of capital to the domestic economy is questionable as the rise in interest rates associated with sterilized intervention may stimulate

further capital inflow perpetuating the problem. Sterilization is effective only if the capital inflow is transitory, not continuing. The economy has to bear the costs of sterilized intervention as well as the crowding-out effect. The Quasi Fiscal costs of Sterilisation involve the exchanging of high yielding domestic assets of Central Bank for low yielding reserves. Disintermediation is promoted if aggressive sterilization is implemented by increasing unremunerated bank reserve requirements.

1.12 Conclusion

From the analysis, it can be concluded that in the post-liberalization era, the Indian Economy faces significant increase in foreign exchange reserves which are accumulated in an effort to withstand the Exchange Market Pressures. The Exchange Market Pressures are associated with increased net capital account flows in the post-liberalization period. The huge accumulation of International Reserves in the post-liberalization period is testimony to the significant resistance offered by the Indian Economy to Exchange Market Pressures. The monetary implication of capital inflows and resistance to exchange market pressures is evidenced by the changing composition of Reserve Money. To prevent capital inflows from affecting monetary base, active sterilized intervention through open market operations are pursued in the Indian Economy. Despite the fact that there are high sterilization efforts to neutralize the impact of Capital Inflows on Reserve Money, the rise in international reserves is transmitted to Broad Money Supply. The sterilization efforts by raising reserve requirements of the banking sector had generally been ineffective in preventing capital flows from affecting Broad Money Supply.

Bibliography

- Aizenman, J. (2004). Financial opening and development: evidence and policy controversies. *American Economic Review*, 94(2), 65-70.
- Aizenman, J. (2008). Large hoarding of international reserves and the emerging global economic architecture. *The Manchester School*, 76(5), 487-503.
- Aizenman, J. (2011). The impossible trinity-from the policy trilemma to the policy quadrilemma Working Papers. *UC Santa Cruz Economics Department*.
- Aizenman, J. (2019). A modern reincarnation of Mundell-Fleming's trilemma. *Economic Modelling*, 81, 444-454.

- Aizenman, J., & Hutchison, M. M. (2012). Exchange market pressure and absorption by international reserves: Emerging markets and fear of reserve loss during the 2008–2009 crisis. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 31(5), 1076-1091.
- Aizenman, J., & Ito, H. (2012). Trilemma policy convergence patterns and output volatility. *The North American Journal of Economics and Finance*, 23(3), 269-285.
- Aizenman, J., & Riera-Crichton, D. (2008). Real exchange rate and international reserves in an era of growing financial and trade integration. *The Review of Economics and Statistics*, 90(4), 812-815.
- Aizenman, J., & Sengupta, R. (2013). Financial Trilemma in China and a Comparative Analysis with India. *Pacific Economic Review*, 18(2), 123-146.
- Aizenman, J., Chinn, M. D., & Ito, H. (2008). *Assessing the emerging global financial architecture: Measuring the trilemma's configurations over time* (No. w14533). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Aizenman, J., Chinn, M. D., & Ito, H. (2010). The emerging global financial architecture: Tracing and evaluating new patterns of the trilemma configuration. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 29(4), 615-641.
- Aizenman, J., Chinn, M. D., & Ito, H. (2011). Surfing the waves of globalization: Asia and financial globalization in the context of the trilemma. *Journal of the Japanese and International Economies*, 25(3), 290-320.
- Aizenman, J., Chinn, M. D., & Ito, H. (2016). Monetary policy spillovers and the trilemma in the new normal: Periphery country sensitivity to core country conditions. *Journal of International Money and Finance*, 68, 298-330.
- Aizenman, J., Jinjarak, Y., & Park, D. (2013). Capital flows and economic growth in the era of financial integration and crisis, 1990–2010. *Open Economies Review*, 24(3), 371-396.
- Baig, M. A., Narasimhan, V., & Ramachandran, M. (2003). Exchange market pressure and the Reserve Bank of India's intervention activity. *Journal of Policy Modeling*, 25(8), 727-748.
- Bleaney, M., Lee, H. A., & Lloyd, T. (2013). Testing the trilemma: exchange rate regimes, capital mobility, and monetary independence. *Oxford Economic Papers*, 65(4), 876-897.
- Girton, L., & Roper, D. (1977). A monetary model of exchange market pressure applied to the postwar Canadian experience. *The American Economic Review*, 67(4), 537-548.

- Goel, S. (2014). An empirical analysis of the relationship between capital flows and the real exchange rate in India. *International Journal of Applied Management and Technology*, 13(1), 5.
- Gopinath, G. (2004). Lending booms, sharp reversals and real exchange rate dynamics. *Journal of International Economics*, 62(1), 1-23.
- Ramachandran, M. (2006). On the upsurge of foreign exchange reserves in India. *Journal of Policy modeling*, 28(7), 797-809.
- Rangarajan, C., & Prasad, A. (2008). Capital flows, exchange rate management and monetary policy. *Macroeconomics and Finance in Emerging Market Economies*, 1(1), 135-149.
- Reinhart, C. M., & Reinhart, V. R. (1999). On the use of reserve requirements in dealing with capital flow problems. *International Journal of Finance & Economics*, 4(1), 27-54.
- Reinhart, C. M., & Reinhart, V. R. (2008). *Capital inflows and reserve accumulation: the recent evidence* (No. w13842). National Bureau of Economic Research.
- Rodrik, D. (2006). The social cost of foreign exchange reserves. *International Economic Journal*, 20(3), 253-266.
- Srinivasan, N., Mahambare, V., & Ramachandran, M. (2009). Preference asymmetry and international reserve accretion in India. *Applied economics letters*, 16(15), 1543-1546.
- Steiner, A. (2017). Central banks and macroeconomic policy choices: Relaxing the trilemma. *Journal of Banking & Finance*, 77, 283-299.